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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADHARSH KS bearing the USN 5SU18PT002 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AISHWARYA N M bearing the USN 5SU18PT004 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AMRITHA K bearing the USN 5SU18PT007 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANAGHA K bearing the USN 5SU18PT008 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANASWARA PURUSHOTHAMAN bearing the USN 5SU18PT009 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANJALI MURALEEDHARAN bearing the USN 5SU18PT010 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARCHANA A S bearing the USN 5SU18PT011 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ASHIFA K A bearing the USN 5SU18PT012 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ASHWAJAKSHI bearing the USN 5SU18PT013 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AVINASH KUMAR bearing the USN 5SU18PT014 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BLESSY MOL T T bearing the USN 5SU18PT015 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BORKAR AMISHA VITTHAL bearing the USN 5SU18PT016 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BRAHMECHA TANVI NARESH bearing the USN 5SU18PT017 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BRUNDA N M bearing the USN 5SU18PT018 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHACKO PRITY PHILIP bearing the USN 5SU18PT019 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CIRIL P BABY bearing the USN 5SU18PT020 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMA THANWEENA bearing the USN 5SU18PT022 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. GOPIKA NANDAN N R bearing the USN 5SU18PT024 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KADAM TRUPTI RAVINDRA bearing the USN 5SU18PT027 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MIDHUN YADUBALAN bearing the USN 5SU18PT030 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUHAMMED ASHRAF bearing the USN 5SU18PT032 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MUSSAMMIL ABDULLA bearing the USN 5SU18PT033 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NAJIL HASHAL A K bearing the USN 5SU18PT034 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NEHA P K bearing the USN 5SU18PT036 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PRATHEEKSHA bearing the USN 5SU18PT037 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RAMYA bearing the USN 5SU18PT039 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SALVI AASTHA TUSHAR bearing the USN 5SU18PT041 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHETTIGAR SUNIL VENKATESH bearing the USN 5SU18PT042 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHETTY SAKSHI SHEKHAR bearing the USN 5SU18PT043 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHETTY SHRAJAL PRABHAKAR bearing the USN 5SU18PT044 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHREYA D S bearing the USN 5SU18PT046 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. STEEPHAN VARGHESE bearing the USN 5SU18PT047 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions**” in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SWATHIKA B R bearing the USN 5SU18PT049 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. TAMATTA SHANTI CHANDU bearing the USN 5SU18PT050 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. WAGHMODE RUCHITA SANJAY bearing the USN 5SU18PT051 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing 2 case reports on Orthopaedic and Neurological conditions”** in the seventh semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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